

MIXED-MODE CRACK PROPAGATION IN HOOP WOUND COMPOSITE
CYLINDERS TESTED IN TORSION

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ABSTRACT

Experimental and theoretical studies are conducted concerning the prediction of fracture mechanisms at the tip of a circumferential pre-crack in thin-walled hoop wound glass reinforced polyester tubes tested in torsion. Mechanical and fracture properties of the tubes are examined as a function of pre-crack length and wall thickness. A finite element method is applied to determine displacement and stress fields in the specimens. It was found that the value of the critical energy release rate G_c estimated using the compliance calibration technique underwent a rapid fall as the pre-crack length increased. Stress intensity factors calculated from numerical displacements at the crack tip revealed that there was a mixed mode fracture for all crack lengths considered. It was shown that the change in fracture behaviour of the tubes was caused by a transition from Mode II to Mode I dominated fracture.

INTRODUCTION

The mechanical properties of composite materials undergoing forward-shear deformation have been the subject of extensive study in the past two decades. In recent years the need to fully characterise such materials prior to use in highly-stressed applications has intensified the need for accurate quantification of mechanical properties in this mode of loading. However mechanical property measurement, and in particular measurement of fracture mechanics parameters, has been compromised by the difficulty involved in selection of a suitable test method. Most analyses of the available test techniques have concluded that torsion of a thin-walled cylinder is the ideal method for shear property determination (1-3). The work described in this paper concerns the measurement of forward-shear (Mode II) fracture parameters using a modified torsion test method. The

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test specimen has been modelled using the finite element method, and the results of this numerical study show good agreement with experimental data.

EXPERIMENTAL DETAILS

A series of cylinders with wall thicknesses ranging from 0.6mm to 2.3mm were manufactured from glass-reinforced polyester by filament winding. The glass type used was Equerove 23/24 (Fibreglass Limited) and the resin was Crystic 272 (Scott-Bader Limited). The fibre reinforcement was aligned in the hoop direction of the specimen and care was taken to ensure that fibre misorientation was minimised.

The standard deviation of individual fibres relating to the mean direction was 1.9° , and the volume fraction of glass in finished specimens was between 0.44 and 0.48.

Specimens were produced with an internal diameter of 50.8mm and a gauge length of 125mm. The geometry of the specimens is shown in Fig.1. All dimensions were chosen in order to fulfil the design criteria for torsion testing specimens determined by [4-6]. The cylinders were bounded to close-fitting end plugs using an epoxy adhesive, and transferred to the testing apparatus in such a manner as to ensure that there was no bending loading.

All dimensions in mm

Fig.1 Specimen geometry

Specimens were subjected to pure torsional loading at a constant rotation rate of $1.6^\circ/\text{hr}$ using a purpose-designed test rig (ESH Limited).

To determine the fracture mechanics parameters G_c and K_{Ic} , circumferential pre-cracks were inserted through the specimen wall, along the fibre direction. A compliance calibration study was performed for each specimen wall thickness, and thus G_c and K_{Ic} could be determined as a function of pre-crack length using the relationship [7]:

$$G_c = \frac{1}{2B} T^2 \frac{dC}{da} \quad (1)$$

C = compliance

a = pre-crack length

B = wall thickness

T = torque

RESULTS

Results from the tests indicated that the insertion of a pre-crack in the cylinder wall changes the response of the specimen to torsional loading. In particular, a number of interesting effects were observed in relation to the maximum shear stress sustained prior to specimen failure. The relationship between shear stress at failure and pre-crack length for each of the series of cylinders tested is shown in Fig.2.

Fig. 2 Shear stress at failure versus crack length for four different wall thicknesses

It is apparent from the series of curves shown in Fig.2 that in all cases the introduction and initial lengthening of the pre-crack had a small effect on the failure stress observed. In each case a rapid fall in shear stress at failure may be detected for crack lengths greater than approximately 7mm. Beyond this rapid fall, further increase in pre-crack length produced little change in the failure stress value. It is also notable that the recorded shear stress at failure increased with increasing wall thickness, the value for uncracked specimens rising by approximately 50% for a fourfold change in wall thickness.

Fig.3 Change in specimen compliance with crack length for four tubes

The change in specimen compliance with increasing pre-crack length for each series of specimens is shown in Fig.3. Using the results from Figs.2 and 3, equation (1) was used to determine the critical strain energy release rate for the material over a range of pre-crack lengths. These results are shown in Fig.4.

Fig.4 Critical energy release rate G_c versus crack lengths

In a similar manner to the failure stress results shown in Fig.2, each curve contains an initial relatively horizontal region, followed by a transition to a lower region. Once again the position of this transition moves to greater pre-crack lengths as specimen wall thickness increased. However, the value of the initial G_c exhibits a slight increase from 3.43kJm^{-2} to 3.89kJm^{-2} for the fourfold increase in wall thickness. It was considered that this apparent reduction in G_c was due to a transition in fracture mode from Mode II fracture at short pre-crack lengths to mixed mode where other fracture modes were involved.

FINITE ELEMENT ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION

To investigate the apparent transition in G_c , a finite element analysis of the specimen under consideration was performed [8]. The PAFEC package was used in this analysis. Three dimensional isoparametric brick and wedge-type elements with orthotropic linear elastic properties were employed. As an example, the finite element mesh with 17.6mm crack length and 1mm wall thickness is shown in Fig.5. Displacements and stresses were

calculated in specimens of each wall thickness, and for pre-crack lengths corresponding to those used in the mechanical tests.

Fig.5 Finite element model of a tube with 17.6mm crack length and 1.0mm wall thickness

Displacement and stress fields in the neighbourhood of the crack tips were analysed to assess possible fracture modes. It was established that a complex displacement field was formed at the crack tips when the specimen was subjected to pure torsional loading [8], and that the displacements were related to Modes I, II and III fracture. Three stress intensity factors K_I , K_{II} and K_{III} could therefore be calculated. It was found for all specimens tested that the computed value of each stress intensity factor increased with pre-crack length. An example of the changes in the stress intensity factors with pre-crack length for a cylinder with wall thickness of 1.75mm is shown in Fig.6.

It is apparent from Fig.6 that the stress intensity factor associated with Mode II fracture (i.e. K_{II}) is predominant across the entire range of crack lengths. The calculated values of K_I and K_{III} are considerably smaller than K_{II} for short crack lengths, though K_{III} becomes more significant as the crack length increases. The stress intensity factor associated with crack opening (K_I) is smaller than K_{III} for all crack lengths. The results implies that the tendency for mixed-mode fracture to occur increases with increasing pre-crack length, and similar results were determined from analysis of specimens with each wall thickness.

Fig.6 Stress intensity factors K_I , K_{II} and K_{III} versus crack length for a tube with 1.75mm wall thickness

In order to describe the fracture behaviour of the specimens, the computed stress intensity factors K_I , K_{II} and K_{III} were compared with previously determined critical values K_{Ic} , K_{IIc} and K_{IIIc} [9]. The critical values were taken to be

$$K_{Ic} = 1.1 \text{MNm}^{-3/2}; \quad K_{IIc} = 8 \text{MNm}^{-3/2}; \quad K_{IIIc} = 4 \text{MNm}^{-3/2}.$$

The calculated stress intensity factors were compared to their known critical values using a general mixed-mode fracture criterion [10] which is given by

$$\left(\frac{K_I}{K_{Ic}}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{K_{II}}{K_{IIc}}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{K_{III}}{K_{IIIc}}\right)^2 = 1 \quad (2)$$

This criterion is an extension of a number of bimodal fracture criteria which have been developed and proven by other workers [11,12].

The stress intensity factors at failure were calculated for each of the specimens tested. The contribution to fracture of each of the components in equation (2) could therefore be evaluated for each crack length and all wall thicknesses. As an example the change in value of each of the terms (K/K_c) with pre-crack length for a specimen with a wall thickness of 1.75mm is shown in Fig.7.

Fig.7 Variation of $(K/K_c)^2$ with crack length

It may be noted from Fig.7 that the Mode II-related term $(K_{II}/K_{IIc})^2$ is predominant through the region of short crack lengths. Over the entire crack length range, the terms $(K_I/K_{Ic})^2$ and $(K_{III}/K_{IIIc})^2$ show a steady rise. The value of the Mode I-related term exceeds that of the Mode II-related component at a pre-crack length of 14mm. Hence it is expected that Mode I-fracture will be dominant from this point. The Mode III fracture component is not significant within the crack length range tested. Figure 7 shows that the change to Mode I dominated fracture coincides with the variation in G_c determined from the mechanical tests

(see Fig.4). Similar results were obtained from analyses of specimens with wall thickness of 0.6, 1.2 and 2.3mm [7,8].

CONCLUSIONS

1. The critical strain energy release rate G_c showed a strong dependence on pre-crack length. A large reduction in G_c occurred over a range of pre-crack lengths between 8 to 14mm.
2. The stress intensity factors are increasing functions of the crack length. There is mixed mode fracture for all crack lengths considered.
3. The observed change in fracture behaviour of filament-wound glass-reinforced polyester tubes tested in torsion is due to transition from Mode II to Mode I dominated fracture.

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